

Accounting for land use changes beyond the farm-level in sustainability assessments: The impact of cocoa production

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Impacts at the farm-level are mostly worse for cocoa agroforestry than full-sun.
- At the landscape level, promoting cocoa agroforestry delivers positive impacts.
- Impacts beyond the farm-level can surpass or contradict those at the farm-level.
- Using proper spatial planning, increased cocoa production can bring positive impacts.
- Impact assessments of cocoa production must take into account land use dynamics.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Impact assessments are used to raise evidence and guide the implementation of sustainability strategies in commodity value chains. Due to methodological and data difficulties, most assessments of agricultural commodities capture the impacts occurring at the farm-level but often dismiss or oversimplify the impacts caused by land use dynamics at larger geographic scale. In this study we analyzed the impacts of two cocoa production systems, full-sun and agroforestry, at the farm-level and beyond the farm-level. We used life cycle assessment to calculate the impacts at the farm-level and a combination of land use modelling with spatial analysis to calculate the impacts beyond the farm-level. We applied this to three different future cocoa production scenarios. The impacts at the farm-level showed that, due to lower yields, cocoa agroforestry performs worse than cocoa full-sun for most impact indicators. However, the impacts beyond the farm-level showed that promoting cocoa agroforestry in the landscape can bring the largest gains in carbon and biodiversity. A scenario analysis of the impacts at the landscape-level showed large nuances depending on the cocoa farming system adopted, market dynamics, and nature conservation policies. The analysis indicated that increasing cocoa demand does not necessarily result in negative impacts for carbon stocks and biodiversity, if sustainable land management and sustainable intensification are adopted. Landscape-level impacts can be larger than farm-level impacts or show completely opposite direction, which highlights the need to complement farm-level assessments with assessments accounting for land use dynamics beyond the farm-level.

1. Introduction

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is one of the most used tools to assess the environmental performance of value chains and guide the implementation of

sustainability strategies in the private sector (Frankl and Rubik, 2000; Hellweg and Canals, 2014; Ibáñez-Forés et al., 2016; Lozano, 2020; Perminova et al., 2016; Stewart et al., 2018). As defined by international standards, LCA is a flexible and versatile tool capable of accounting for a

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wide range of impacts caused by industrial activities, especially those of highly manufactured products (ISO 14044, 2006; JRC-IES, 2010; UNEP-SETAC, 2016, 2019). Despite of this flexibility, existing data and methodological challenges can limit the completeness of LCA studies, especially for value chains that involve agricultural commodities (Curran, 2014; Finkbeiner et al., 2014; Godar et al., 2016; Haas et al., 2000; Kløverpris et al., 2020; Notarnicola et al., 2017; Reap et al., 2008a, 2008b; Roy et al., 2009). Agricultural practices are highly diverse and their impacts are strongly dependent on contextual factors such as climatic conditions and landscape patterns. Therefore, accounting for the impacts of value chains using agricultural commodities requires highly specific data on farming practices, local conditions and contextual factors of the landscapes where farming occurs (De Rosa, 2018; Hellweg and Canals, 2014; Milà i Canals et al., 2007; Notarnicola et al., 2017). However, this information is often difficult to obtain due to the limited traceability and transparency of sourcing areas faced by global commodity supply chains such as cocoa (Boström et al., 2015; Gardner et al., 2018; Hellweg and Canals, 2014).

Land use change is one of the main drivers of global environmental change and is responsible for about a third of total greenhouse gas emissions (Crippa et al., 2021; Foley et al., 2005; IPCC, 2019a; Lambin et al., 2001). Agriculture is a major driver of land use change, therefore, it is important that impact assessments of agriculture account for the land use change effects that farming causes beyond the farm-level (Finkbeiner et al., 2014; Notarnicola et al., 2017; Searchinger et al., 2008; Teillard et al., 2016; Van Asselen and Verburg, 2013). The impacts of agriculture are partly determined by the agrochemical usage, farm management practices, and biophysical conditions on the production site (Dijkman et al., 2012; Millard et al., 2021; Seufert and Ramankutty, 2017). However, agriculture can trigger indirect land use displacements and cause environmental degradation beyond the farm-level because, being embedded into socioeconomic systems, it is in constant competition for land resources with other economic activities (Liu et al., 2013; Meyfroidt et al., 2013, 2018). These land use changes depend on land suitability and opportunity costs, and are regulated by spatial policies and market forces (Turner et al., 2020; Van Asselen and Verburg, 2013). Therefore, the environmental impact of agriculture is ultimately determined by the landscape configuration, the location of farming and intensity of agricultural practices (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2015; Dullinger et al., 2021). For instance, previous studies have found that the indirect impacts of agricultural production on carbon and biodiversity may far exceed the impacts occurring on the agricultural field itself. The conclusions of impact assessment studies accounting for land use changes beyond the farm-level may therefore contradict conclusions taken on the basis of farm-level assessments (Barnes et al., 2017; Hellweg and Canals, 2014; Lapola et al., 2010; Magliocca et al., 2020; Richards et al., 2014; Searchinger et al., 2008). If indirect land use impacts are not taken into account, sustainability governance initiatives of agriculture-based value chains may unknowingly displace environmental burdens across places (Curran, 2014; Hellweg and Canals, 2014).

Recent developments in the LCA community are helping to close this gap by increasing the spatial resolution of impact characterization factors (Blonk Consultants, 2021; BSI, 2012; Bulle et al., 2019; Chaudhary et al., 2015; Veronesi et al., 2020), expanding LCA agricultural databases (Blonk Consultants, 2019a, 2019b; Koch and Salou, 2014; Weidema et al., 2013), and complementing LCA with additional methods (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2017; Crawford et al., 2018; Othoniel et al., 2019). Nevertheless, most of the methods used to account for land use change impacts in LCA have limitations to capture the fine-scale spatial dynamics arising from socioecological interactions (Earles and Halog, 2011; Finkbeiner, 2014; Milà i Canals et al., 2007; Schmidt et al., 2015). Such LCA assessments of spatial dynamics are usually based on economic models, biophysical models or normative rules, and often define coarse units of impact (e.g. administrative units) or generalize cause-effect relationships to some degree (Schmidt et al., 2015). Consequential LCA is one of the methods most suited to assess the impacts beyond the farm-level, however, it also does so from a broader perspective by accounting for the effect of global market dynamics (JRC-IES, 2010; Weidema, 2003). Despite these efforts, LCA studies that

anticipate and account for impacts caused by land use change are far from mainstream and often only address limited components of land use dynamics (Roca and Searcy, 2012; Schmidt et al., 2015). Sustainability initiatives in agricultural producing landscapes will benefit from complementing farm-level assessments with methods capable of accounting for fine-scale land use dynamics (Hellweg and Canals, 2014; Notarnicola et al., 2017; Parra Paitan and Verburg, 2019).

While several LCA studies accounting for land use change exist for biofuels, other crops have gotten limited attention and no study on cocoa exist to our knowledge (Di Lucia et al., 2012; McManus and Taylor, 2015; Palmer and Owens, 2015; Prapasongsa and Gheewala, 2016; Searchinger et al., 2008; Somé et al., 2018). We used the case of cocoa production in Ghana, the second-largest cocoa producing country, to advance the assessment of impacts caused by land use dynamics beyond the farm-level. Cocoa is an important agricultural commodity whose supply chain is responsible for the conversion of large areas of tropical rainforest (Fountain and Huetz-Adams, 2020; Goldman et al., 2020; Pendrill et al., 2019). Our goal is to complement a farm-level assessment with a method that captures fine-scale spatial land use dynamics beyond the farm-level. We conducted an attributional LCA to assess impacts of cocoa the farm-level and a combination of land use modelling and spatial analysis to account for the impacts beyond the farm-level. We analyzed differences in the magnitude of impacts and discussed the implications of land use dynamics for the sustainability governance of value chains that involve an agricultural phase.

2. Materials and methods

According to climatic factors, Ghana is subdivided into three main ecological zones: the savannah zone, the transitional zone, and the high forest zone (HFZ). Our study area comprises the HFZ, which is the southernmost area located within the Guinean forests of West Africa. The HFZ is subdivided into nine vegetation zones (Supplementary Material F), in which annual precipitation varies between 1000 and 2200 mm, mean temperatures vary between 25 and 27 °C, and soils are predominantly acidic (Ochrosols and Oxysoils) (Forestry Commission, 2015, 2017; Salifu, 1997).

We used a land cover map of the HFZ of Ghana for the year 2015 (Wolff et al., 2020). This map reported nine land use classes: built-up areas, water bodies, mining, rubber plantations, closed forest, open forest, cocoa, mixed forest with agriculture, and agriculture with sparse tree cover (Fig. 3). Closed forest differs in tree cover percentage from open forest (>50% and <30%, respectively), and the last two land use classes are primarily food crop production areas with different tree cover values (>30% for mixed forest with agriculture, and <30% for agriculture with sparse tree cover).

First, we used LCA to quantify the farm-level environmental impacts of producing one kilogram of cocoa beans under two different farming systems: cocoa full-sun (i.e. cocoa monocrops) and cocoa agroforestry (i.e. cocoa cultivated along with shade trees). In this stage, our goal was to calculate the impacts caused by cocoa production at the farm-level, therefore we use an attributional life cycle assessment. We complemented this farm-level accounting with the impacts caused beyond the farm-level due to land use dynamics. We combined land use modelling and spatial analysis to calculate changes in biodiversity and carbon stocks beyond the farm-level. We accounted impacts in three different future scenarios depicting increases in cocoa demand (Fig. 1). We then compared the impacts calculated at the farm-level and beyond. See Supplementary Material A for an overview of the main methods and data sources used.

2.1. Attributional life cycle assessment

Although multiple paid life cycle inventory databases and LCA software packages with embedded methods exist, we decided to use open-source tools as these are accessible to most stakeholders.

Fig. 1. Overview of the methods used to account for the impacts of cocoa production in Ghana.

2.1.1. Goal and scope

The boundaries of the system were defined strictly around the agricultural phase, including the application of agrochemicals and the use of land. Cocoa production in Ghana is mainly rain-fed and is not mechanized. Therefore, water consumption was not considered and the use of machinery comprised only the use of pesticide sprayers. We defined the functional unit as one kilogram of cocoa beans ready for further processing (post-fermentation on farm or field).

2.1.2. Life cycle inventory

The life cycle inventory was based on a previous LCA study about cocoa production in Ghana (Ntiamoah, 2009; Ntiamoah and Afrane, 2008). Based on this study we differentiated the inventory for two cocoa production systems: cocoa agroforestry and full-sun. This differentiation followed literature reporting farming inputs and yields for these cocoa systems (Abdulai et al., 2018; Asare et al., 2019; Bymolt et al., 2018). In first place we had to determine the yields for each cocoa production system. To do this, we used the relative yields for agroforestry and full-sun as reported by Abdulai et al. (2018) and adapted these to match the cocoa volume produced in the regions included in our study area (Ghana Statistical Service, 2019). To make this calculation, we multiplied the reported yields by Abdulai et al. (2018) by an adjustment factor. This adjustment factor (0.82) was calculated by dividing the cocoa volume produced in the study area (Ghana Statistical Service, 2019) by the volume that would be produced if we would use the yields reported by Abdulai et al. for the study area. The final yield values were set to 418 and 525 kg/ha of cocoa beans for cocoa agroforestry and full-sun systems, respectively. Following data from Abdulai et al. (2018), fertilizer usage in cocoa full-sun systems was set as twice the amount used in cocoa agroforestry systems. Pesticide usage was considered equal for both cocoa systems because these are applied homogeneously by the Cocoa Pest and Disease Control Agency of Ghana (Abdulai et al., 2018). For the same reason, the petrol quantity needed for pesticide spraying was considered equal for both systems. The calculation of pesticide emissions followed the PestLCI 2.0 model (Dijkman et al., 2012). The calculation of fertilizer emissions was based on Ecoinvent methodologies (Nemecek and Kagi, 2007; Nemecek and Schnetzer, 2011; Prasuhn, 2006). A more detailed description of the inventory of inputs and outputs can be found in the Supplementary Material B and C.

2.1.3. Life cycle impact assessment

The life cycle impact assessment of the following indicators was based on the IMPACT World+ model (Bulle et al., 2019): acidification potential, eutrophication potential, freshwater eco-toxicity potential, global warming potential, human toxicity potential, and disability-adjusted life years (DALY). The disability-adjusted life years (DALY) refers to the number of years of life lost due to the negative impacts of toxic substances on human health. We used the potential permanent disappeared fraction of species indicator (PDF) to calculate the impacts of land use change on biodiversity loss (Chaudhary et al., 2015; Jolliet et al., 2018). We selected this method over the one proposed by De Baan et al. (2013) following the suggestion of the UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative (UNEP-SETAC, 2016). This choice also allowed comparability with the biodiversity indicator used in the spatial assessment. However, since the meaning and unit of this indicator is different from other indicators from the IMPACT World+ model (Bulle et al., 2019), its interpretation was done independently from other impact indicators. As a consequence, the damage indicator used for biodiversity only accounted for the effects of land use change and not the effect of the use of agrochemicals. The impact of land use change on carbon emissions was calculated based on the PAS2050-1 methodology (BSI, 2012) according to the “country known, previous land use known” treatment, which amortizes impacts over 20 years. As advised, we replaced the default emission factors with those reported for each type of land conversion in each type of vegetation zone of Ghana (Kongsager et al., 2013). More details about the impact assessment methods used can be found in the Supplementary Material D.

2.2. Land use modelling of future scenarios

We defined three scenarios to simulate future land use conversions caused by cocoa production: a) *Green Development*, b) *Intensive Agriculture Development*, and c) *Regulated Investments*. We used the CLUMondo model (Van Asselen and Verburg, 2013) to simulate future land use changes in our study area. CLUMondo makes a spatially explicit allocation of future land use changes following an iterative process in which land use types compete for land to satisfy external demands of resources. This allocation is based on location suitability (e.g. biophysical factors), spatial policies (e.g. protected areas), land conversion elasticity, and the capacity of each land use type to provide specific resources.

The definition and quantification of scenarios was done according to the shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) (O'Neill et al., 2017). The *Green Development*, *Intensive Agriculture Development*, and *Regulated Investments* scenarios were framed around SSP1, SSP5, and SSP3, respectively. The scenarios differ in terms of market demand, but mostly differ in the cocoa farming system encouraged to satisfy this demand (agroforestry or full-sun) and the implemented forest protection policies (Table 1). Simulations were done for a 15-year period, from 2015 until 2030. In short, *Green Development* tried to satisfy an increase in cocoa demand while avoiding deforestation and promoting cocoa agroforestry systems. In *Intensive Agriculture Development* there was a slightly higher increase in cocoa demand (consistent with the focus on agricultural development), little attention to forest protection, and a strong adoption of cocoa full-sun systems. *Regulated Investments* was an intermediate scenario where cocoa agroforestry and full-sun were given equal opportunity while also protecting forests. We set specific demand changes for rubber production as it is an important cash crop in Ghana. Cocoa yields changed over time to simulate agricultural intensification. In the *Green Development* scenario, only cocoa agroforestry yields were gradually increased up to the national target (1000 kg/ha) (Ministry of Food and Agriculture of Ghana, 2016). In the *Intensive Agriculture Development* scenario, only cocoa full-sun yields were similarly increased, and in *Regulated Investments* yields were increased for both cocoa farming systems up to the same threshold (Ministry of Food and Agriculture of Ghana, 2016; Wessel and Quist-Wessel, 2015). These yield increases followed government targets and are moderate in contrast to yields reported by other experimental studies (Bymolt et al., 2018; Wessel and Quist-Wessel, 2015).

Using the initial land cover map as a basis, we differentiated cocoa agroforestry and cocoa full-sun from the general cocoa class. This differentiation was done using high-resolution tree cover data (Hansen et al., 2013). To get the tree cover in cocoa producing areas for the year 2015 we added tree cover gains (2000–2012, only data available) and subtracted tree cover losses (2000–2015) to the tree cover map for the year 2000. We defined pixels with more than 55% of tree cover as cocoa agroforestry and the remaining ones as cocoa full-sun, in line with studies citing tree cover values of cocoa agroforestry systems in Ghana and their total relative area (FAO, 2014; Tutu Benefoh et al., 2018). For the land use simulation we defined the suitability of pixels for each land use type using a combination of 17 physical and socioeconomic variables (Supplementary Material E). Suitability was defined after testing the relationship between these variables and the actual distribution of land uses using logistic regression functions with stepwise elimination. The capacity of each pixel to provide resources (i.e. cocoa, food, rubber, tree cover, and built-up areas) was defined using subnational production statistics of cocoa, rubber, and food crops (based on cassava, maize, and plantain) for 2015 (Ghana Statistical Service, 2019). Future demands and yield increases were defined according to country-level quantifications of SSPs for built-up areas, food crops, and cocoa (IFPRI, 2017; IIASA, 2020; Riahi et al., 2017; Sulser et al., 2015). We used official national targets on forest protection, restoration, and forest plantation to define the future demand of forest areas (Dave et al., 2019; Forestry Commission, 2016; Republic of Ghana, 2017). Due to the lack of official projected data on future rubber demand, we used linear projections of historical rubber production statistics (2000–2015; FAOSTAT, 2020), similarly for all scenarios. Further details on the settings of the model can be found in the Supplementary Material E.

2.3. Spatial analysis of impacts on carbon and biodiversity

Using spatial analysis, we identified the pixels converted from and into cocoa in each modelled scenario. Consequently, we calculated changes in

carbon stocks and biodiversity using official carbon emission factors for Ghana (Forestry Commission, 2017) and the GLOBIO-InVEST model (Alkemade et al., 2009; Natural Capital Project, 2020; Sharp et al., 2018), respectively.

The Forestry Commission of Ghana reports carbon emission factors (tCO₂eq/ha) per vegetation zone and for each land use conversion (between closed forest, open forest, cocoa, oil palm, rubber, cropland, grasslands, settlements, and bare land) (Kongsager et al., 2013). To avoid perverse incentives for deforestation, this study reported zero emissions for conversions of natural vegetation that caused carbon sequestration increases (e.g. from dry semi-deciduous zones to cocoa farms). Therefore, we recalculated these emission factors using the same methodology. Moreover, we adapted the values to our specific land use classes using the broader literature on carbon in forest systems. The cocoa emission factors reported were assigned to our cocoa agroforestry class because the original study calculated these emissions in cocoa farms having characteristics equivalent to our cocoa agroforestry class (Kongsager et al., 2013). Cocoa full-sun emission factors were calculated based on the reported cocoa agroforestry/full-sun carbon ratio for Ghana (Isaac et al., 2007). The emission factors reported for cropland were assigned to the agriculture sparse tree land cover class. The values for the mixed forest with agriculture land use class were calculated as the average of cocoa agroforestry and cropland. To find the final cocoa-driven carbon stock change in each scenario at the landscape-level, the corresponding emission factors were multiplied by the respective area of converted land.

The GLOBIO-InVEST model calculates changes in biodiversity associated with land use change, habitat fragmentation, and infrastructure (Sharp et al., 2018). This model uses the mean species abundance indicator (MSA) as an indicator of biodiversity, which is an aggregate metric reflecting the richness and abundance of species in a certain area in comparison to its pristine state. Accordingly, a MSA of value 1 indicates that biodiversity is in a pristine state while 0 indicates that it has been decimated. In GLOBIO-InVEST, MSA values were available for eleven land use types. We matched our land use classes to these eleven land use classes, applying the MSA values of 'plantation forest' to rubber plantations, those of 'secondary vegetation' to open forest, those of 'low input agriculture' to mixed forest with agriculture, agriculture with sparse tree cover & cocoa full-sun, and those of 'agroforestry' to our cocoa agroforestry class. Finally, we applied the standard values of forest fragmentation on MSA (Alkemade et al., 2009) and used the road network of Ghana to calculate impacts of infrastructure (UN-OCHA, 2020). The GLOBIO-InVEST model calculates changes in biodiversity by multiplying the MSA values of land use change, habitat fragmentation, and infrastructure in each pixel. The impact of cocoa production on biodiversity corresponded to the average MSA value of the land areas converted. Same as for carbon, this was used to calculate the impacts of cocoa production in the entire landscape for each modelled scenario. Further details about the calculation of carbon and biodiversity changes can be found in the Supplementary Material F.

3. Results

3.1. Impacts of cocoa production at the farm-level

According to LCA, the production of one kilogram of cocoa beans under cocoa full-sun farming systems caused on average 22% less negative impacts on air, water, and soils (indicators: acidification potential, freshwater ecotoxicity, freshwater eutrophication, and global warming potential) than under cocoa agroforestry systems. This was due to the higher yields of

Table 1

Main characteristics of each scenario. Population and food demand increase similarly in all scenarios. AF = cocoa agroforestry; FS = cocoa full-sun.

	Forest protection policies	Cocoa farming system encouraged	Cocoa demand	Rubber demand	Cocoa yields
Green Development	Yes	Cocoa agroforestry	Increased 27%	Decreased 20%	Increased for AF maintained for FS
Intensive Agriculture Development	No	Cocoa full-sun	Increased 40%	Increased 57%	Maintained for AF increased for FS
Regulated Investments	Yes	Cocoa agroforestry & cocoa full-sun	Increased 33%	Increased 60%	Increased for AF increased for FS

cocoa full-sun using the same amount of pesticides per hectare. However, cocoa full-sun was on average 60% more harmful to human health (human toxicity and DALY) due to the higher use of fertilizers, particularly because of emissions to surface water such as copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), and lead (Pb) (see Supplementary Material C). Nevertheless, due to its farming intensity, cocoa full-sun was almost three times more harmful to biodiversity (PDF). Because of higher yields, cocoa full-sun farms required less land area than cocoa agroforestry to produce one kilogram of cocoa beans. Therefore, carbon emissions due to land use change were 18% lower for cocoa full-sun than for cocoa agroforestry. Interestingly, the carbon emissions caused by land use change were almost 300 times higher than those caused by the use of agricultural inputs (Fig. 2).

3.2. Land use change impacts of cocoa production

The 2030 landscape configurations that resulted from the land use modelling determined the magnitude of the impacts of cocoa production beyond the farm-level (Fig. 3). The *Green Development* scenario led to a trifold expansion of cocoa agroforestry systems (Figs. 4 and 5). This expansion was mainly achieved by replacing degraded forest areas and slightly reducing the rubber plantation area. At the same time, 30% of primary forests areas (ca. 294 kha) were restored and 44% of cocoa full-sun areas were converted into more sustainable food agroforestry systems. The *Intensive Agriculture Development* scenario achieved land-sparing, thereby reducing the cocoa full-sun area by 21%. However, the limited environmental protection in this scenario led to the displacement of cocoa full-sun to the south-western region, displacing 43% of the remaining primary forest areas (ca. 426 kha). In the *Regulated Investments* scenario, cocoa full-sun and agroforestry areas were reduced by 31% and 30%, respectively, while 10% of primary forests areas were restored.

3.3. Impacts of cocoa production beyond the farm-level in each scenario

The impacts of land use change on carbon and biodiversity in each scenario were strongly nuanced at the landscape-level (Fig. 6). Land conversions to meet cocoa demand caused 62 MtCO₂eq of net carbon gains in the *Green Development* scenario, 14 MtCO₂eq of net carbon gains in the *Regulated Investments* scenario, and 52 MtCO₂eq of net carbon losses in the *Intensive Agriculture Development* scenario. The *Regulated Investments* scenario showed the largest biodiversity gains, closely followed by the *Green Development* scenario, while the *Intensive Agriculture Development*

scenario showed biodiversity losses. In the *Green Development* scenario carbon and biodiversity gains were due to the expansion of cocoa agroforestry into formerly degraded forest areas (ca. 30 MtCO₂eq gain, ca. 0.006 MSA gain) and the large conversion of cocoa full-sun farms into food agroforestry systems (ca. 31 MtCO₂eq gain, ca. 0.2 MSA gain) (Fig. 6). The *Regulated Investments* scenario showed carbon and biodiversity gains (ca. 14 MtCO₂eq, ca. 0.04 MSA) mainly due to reduction of cocoa full-sun areas. This reduction created abandoned areas that were later followed by ecological succession and resulted in gains of carbon and biodiversity. The *Intensive Agriculture Development* scenario showed large carbon and biodiversity loss (ca. 52 MtCO₂eq, ca. 0.1 MSA) associated with the replacement of primary forest, in line with the assumed weak forest protection policies. This occurred because the weak forest protection policies encouraged the migration of cocoa full-sun farms into highly fertile forest soils.

At the farm-level, life cycle assessment resulted in larger carbon losses for cocoa agroforestry systems. However, at the landscape-level, the spatial assessment found larger carbon losses in the scenario encouraging cocoa full-sun systems (*Intensive Agriculture Development*) and found carbon gains in scenarios promoting cocoa agroforestry. Carbon loss at the landscape-level was almost the same (83%) as at the farm-level in the *Intensive Agriculture Development* scenario. Carbon gains at the landscape-level were double the gains at the farm-level in the *Green Development* scenario. At the farm-level, the *Regulated Investments* scenario showed net carbon gains while at the farm-level it showed a small carbon loss. At the farm-level, biodiversity loss occurs in all scenarios while at the landscape-level losses occur only in the *Intensive Agriculture Development* scenario (almost double the farm-level loss). The impacts of cocoa production at the landscape-level are a result of the different scenarios settings and highlight the important role of the socioeconomic context.

4. Discussion

Our results reinforce previous findings in the field and highlight the importance of analyzing the impacts of land use dynamics caused by agricultural production. Our study found that: 1) the impacts of land use change are best accounted for when placed in the corresponding spatial context, 2) the impacts of land use change span beyond agricultural production units and trigger indirect impacts that need to be included in impact assessments, 3) land use interactions need to be evaluated in a non-linear manner by considering the dynamics of competing land uses in light of context-dependent factors, 4) farm management choices have a strong influence

Fig. 2. Impacts of cocoa full-sun and agroforestry per kilogram of cocoa beans at the farm-level. Units for each impact category are shown within parenthesis. The first six are mid-point indicators and the last two are end-point indicators. Land use carbon emissions correspond to the weighted average reported by PAS2050-1 method.

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of land use types in initial (a) and modelled years (b-d).

on the intensity of impacts beyond the farm-level and these differences need to be captured in impact assessments. We elaborate on these findings and the policy implications in the coming paragraphs.

4.1. Trade-offs of including or excluding land use dynamics in impact assessments

This study found that for full accounting, impact assessments of cocoa production need to be contextualized in the producing landscape since this allows to capture fine-scale land use dynamics. The impacts of cocoa production did not increase linearly with increasing demand but were, instead, strongly dependent on local socioeconomic factors that ultimately

determined the spatial configuration of producing landscapes (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2015; Garrett et al., 2013; Koellner and Scholz, 2007; Richards, 2021). Market forces, land use planning, agricultural policies, farm management strategies, and environmental regulation policies influenced this final spatial allocation and, therefore, the impacts of cocoa production beyond the farm-level (De Rosa, 2018; Hellweg and Canals, 2014; McManus and Taylor, 2015; Meyfroidt et al., 2018; Turner et al., 2020; Van Asselen and Verburg, 2013). According to our study, increasing cocoa demands do not necessarily go together with negative environmental impacts. Positive impacts can be achieved if sustainable intensification, forest protection, and sustainable farming systems (cocoa agroforestry) are encouraged in the landscape. Increasing demand threatened forest areas only in the absence of these regulatory and protection measures.

When the impacts of cocoa production are calculated at the farm-level, cocoa full-sun seemed to balance better the trade-offs between sustainability and productivity by having higher yields and showing lower impacts for most midpoint impact indicators than cocoa agroforestry. These findings are in line with other studies reporting that, due to lower yields, sustainable production systems perform better per unit of area than per unit of product (Andres et al., 2016; Blaser et al., 2017, 2018; Cucurachi et al., 2019; Jacobi et al., 2014; Mortimer et al., 2018; Seufert and Ramankutty, 2017). Our results on the impacts of cocoa production on carbon and biodiversity at the farm-level are in line with previous studies reporting larger negative impacts for cocoa full-sun systems (Andres et al., 2016; Blaser et al., 2018; Jacobi et al., 2014). The analysis beyond the farm-level showed that, in the absence of other protection measures, the promotion of cocoa full-sun systems could generate more detrimental impacts due to land use change, especially for biodiversity and carbon emissions. This means that promoting high-yield cocoa systems could help reduce the net cocoa area but, without sustainable intensification and forest conservation measures, this jeopardizes the sustainability of cocoa landscapes. The largest carbon fixation and biodiversity gains were obtained when promoting forest conservation and encouraging cocoa agroforestry systems at the same time (Green Development scenario). However, to also deliver socioeconomic benefits, this strategy must consider adequate shade levels in agroforestry systems to avoid negative trade-offs between cocoa yields and biodiversity

Fig. 4. Changes in the area of land use types between the initial (2015) and modelled years (2030, the last three bars).

Fig. 5. Area of cocoa full-sun (a) and cocoa agroforestry (b) gained and lost to other land use types in each scenario. Positive values represent cocoa areas gained to previous land uses while negative values represent cocoa areas lost to other land uses.

Fig. 6. Impacts of cocoa production on biodiversity and greenhouse gas within all cocoa farms (farm-level) and beyond them (landscape-level). Impacts are shown for the entire study area and each scenario. Positive values indicate losses in biodiversity or carbon (emissions) while negative values indicate gains (i.e. gains in biodiversity or carbon sequestration).

(Andres et al., 2016; Asare et al., 2019; Blaser et al., 2017; Phalan et al., 2011). Moreover, restored closed forest areas could only bring the full expected carbon and biodiversity gains if they remain standing for at least 80 years (Cole et al., 2014; Martin et al., 2013).

The characterization factors used for carbon emissions due to land use change differed from those reported by the intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC). The latter reports much lower carbon emission factors for agroforestry and perennial monocrops in tropical areas (88 and 110–146 tCO₂eq, respectively) (IPCC, 2019b) than those used by this study (on average 250 and 187 CO₂eq, respectively). This difference emerged because IPCC factors were obtained by averaging the emissions from various cropping systems within a wide range of tropical forests, while the values used by this study followed local carbon measurements in cocoa farms in each vegetation zone of Ghana. This once again highlights the importance of using spatial explicit assessments that take into account previous land uses and the local context in which the cultivation takes place.

4.2. Practical implications for practitioners and potential ways of improvement

The large negative impacts of cocoa full-sun on human toxicity could be solved with improved fertilizer use. The low productivity of cocoa agroforestry systems could be improved through sustainable yield increases. Sustainable yield increases balance environmental benefits with productivity increases by combining improved use of agrochemicals, sanitation practices (weeding, pruning, thinning), and, in some cases, cocoa tree replanting (Carodenuto, 2019). These improved farm management practices have a strong influence on the environmental impacts but require investments in farm training and enabling policy environments (Blaser et al., 2018; Costa et al., 2020; Erb et al., 2017; Kleppel, 2020; Schulze et al., 2019).

Companies could benefit from the inclusion of land use dynamics in the assessment of impacts by showing that business goals, if managed properly in the landscape, do not necessarily contradict sustainability goals. By making more contextualized assessments of impacts, companies can not only anticipate future changes caused by their sourcing strategies but can also help to strengthen the very much needed trust of consumers (Gardner et al., 2018; Lambin et al., 2018). Such assessments could also help companies to have more accurate information on the extent of their environmental impacts, and help them improving the scope of their sustainability strategies. Our results suggested that cocoa sourcing strategies (in terms of volume and location) may have much larger impacts than those usually accounted for by methods that do not account for fine-scale land use dynamics. Therefore, companies might be not only making decisions based on incomplete information but might be also missing the opportunity to demonstrate environmental gains in the landscape due to sustainable initiatives. Companies could reduce impacts by fostering investments in activities that drive positive impacts in the entire landscape, such as sustainable yield increases or more sustainable farming systems.

To effectively minimize negative impacts, transparent coordination of private and public actors is necessary for the assessment, management, and monitoring stages of sustainability actions (Folke et al., 2019; Lambin et al., 2018). Because cocoa farms are embedded in socioeconomic systems, isolated initiatives coming from any sector are insufficient to tackle sustainability challenges caused by land use change. Our study has shown that the overall landscape management and its configuration is a large determinant of the impacts of cocoa production. On the one hand, clear land use planning and regulatory policies are needed to guide companies' business goals and sourcing strategies. At the same time, companies need to assess the landscape-level implications of future business strategies. The jurisdictional approach is an increasingly promoted strategy used to govern the impacts of farming systems beyond the farm-level. By engaging multiple stakeholders in the planning of sustainability interventions at the landscape-level, the jurisdictional approach aims at minimizing the risk of displacing negative outcomes of cocoa farming into other parts of the landscape (Boshoven et al., 2021; von Essen et al., 2021). In support of these initiatives, the LCA research community is increasingly promoting the

landscape approach with the aim of better capturing the effect that landscape configurations have on the agricultural impacts. By capturing the impacts that expand beyond farming units (e.g. biodiversity loss, soil degradation, indirect land use change), this approach also helps to prevent LCA studies from being bias towards highly-intensive farming systems (van der Werf et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2021). Jurisdictional approaches can benefit from the inclusion of land use dynamics in the assessment of impacts of cocoa production, as shown in this study.

4.3. Challenges for the inclusion of land use change impacts beyond the farm-level

Instead of our combination of land use modelling and spatial analysis we could have used consequential LCA (CLCA) to evaluate the impacts beyond the farm-level. CLCA is a tool that integrates economic modelling to assess the consequences of value chain decisions on physical flows and impacts (Earles and Halog, 2011; Prox and Curran, 2017). However, CLCA would have done so from a global economic perspective and defining coarser units of analysis, while our goal was to address fine-scale land use dynamics occurring at the landscape-level. Our land use modelling approach also accounted for broad scale economic dynamics by defining demand shifts according to the outputs of computable general equilibrium models (e.g. IMAGE), embedded in the SSP scenarios that guided our local scenarios. Although our study area only covered a small part of the world, it is second most important cocoa production area and thus, the analysis, has importance even from a global perspective.

Although the LCA community has widely acknowledged the importance of accounting for land use change impacts on biodiversity and carbon emissions, the inclusion of these indicators remains limited in practice (Knudsen et al., 2020; Winter et al., 2017). LCA remains a very useful tool to account for the toxicity impacts of agricultural production on humans and ecosystems. However, sustainability practitioners in the corporate sector should seek to complement LCA assessments with tools able to capture the fine-scale land use dynamics spanning beyond the farm-level (Crenna et al., 2020; McManus and Taylor, 2015; Parra Paitan and Verburg, 2019; Raschio et al., 2018). One complication is that in practice, due to the high complexity and fragmentation of supply chains, companies usually do not know the exact origin of the products they use. Due to the high cost and logistic complications of achieving full traceability, companies' assessments have often limited spatial resolution and are not able to capture the local impacts caused by land use dynamics. Therefore, achieving full traceability of agricultural commodities is one of the first challenges to complete (Gardner et al., 2018; Ingram et al., 2018). As more of these initiatives emerge in different supply chains, multi-stakeholder platforms become necessary to ensure consistency and reliability (Folke et al., 2019). This would require setting adequate open and independent monitoring and reporting systems alongside corporate sustainability strategies (Lambin et al., 2018). The latter would benefit from a close collaboration of companies with organizations holding information about local landscapes (e.g. government for providing land use maps or scoping future regulatory policies).

4.4. Limitations and ways forward

The life cycle inventory data and characterization factors for impact indicators may vary greatly (and might even overlap) depending on soil type, tree age, phenology stage, cocoa variety, farm management practices, and local climatic conditions (Blaser et al., 2018). The data and factors used in this study did not provide information on these variations reflecting the actual variability in yields, agrochemical inputs, biodiversity composition and carbon stocks in cocoa farms. Therefore, we did not incorporate such variability. If available, impact assessments could refine the results by considering variability ranges when comparing cocoa farming systems.

Indirect nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions that result from the mineralization of organic matter were not accounted for because of the lack of characterization factors differentiating cocoa agroforestry and full-sun systems under our study conditions. Land use change can generate N₂O emissions

but in the long term they are mainly determined by nitrogen input rates (Corré, 2002; Veldkamp et al., 2008; Verchot et al., 2020). Therefore, this omission might have had limited implications giving the absence of nitrogen fertilizers in our case study.

The land use model used allowed us to account for potential indirect impacts caused by cocoa demand and production within the Ghanaian HFZ. However, it did not capture spillovers beyond it. This means that we could not assess the impacts that sustainability strategies in this area could cause in other cocoa-producing landscapes or countries. Because land resources are limited, spillovers and leakages may emerge in different locations. Therefore, the conclusions made in this study are only valid in the given context. The integration of other modelling methods may help to address this challenge (e.g. computable general equilibrium models) (Cucurachi et al., 2019; Hellweg and Canals, 2014; Parra Paitan and Verburg, 2019).

The land use model considered cocoa yield increases that require changes in farm management practices (i.e. agrochemical usage). Due to lack of documentation, we did not include the impacts of the new farm management practices. If these include a higher agrochemical usage part of the benefits of the yield increases would be offset by the impacts of increased agrochemical use. Therefore, sustainable intensification with more efficient input use and improved management techniques should be used to avoid such an increase in impacts.

We used internally consistent scenarios of plausible changes in socioeconomic context, cocoa demand and production conditions rather than an experimental approach in which production quantity is standardized. Our approach prioritized such a scenario approach over comparative capacity as cocoa is embedded in a socioeconomic system that also changes when cocoa demand changes. Therefore, it was important to keep consistency in all other socioeconomic factors linked to cocoa production. This way, our results are easier to apply to reality but, at the same time, they did not allow us to completely isolate the effects of cocoa production. Because cocoa production is dominant in the landscape and one of the strongest drivers of land use change, the risk of false impact attribution was minimal.

The land use model did not account for lag-times in the production of perennial crops and, due to the data limitations explained in the Methods section, the effect of price fluctuation on rubber demand was not considered when defining future rubber demand scenarios. The impacts of changing rubber demands remained constrained to the southern non-cocoa producing area due to land suitability. Therefore, this hardly affected the spatial allocation of cocoa farms. Oil palm is another cash crop present in the landscape however, due to lack of spatial data, we could not include it in the analysis.

Finally, we acknowledge that this study mainly addresses environmental impacts and did not address the socioeconomic trade-offs that could arise as a result of sustainability initiatives. Worrying problems linked to cocoa production such as poverty and child labor need to be assessed alongside to balance the suggestions taken based on environmental assessments (De Rosa, 2018; Onat et al., 2017; Ruf, 2011; Sala et al., 2013).

5. Conclusions

This study shows that the impacts of cocoa production can only be accurately accounted for when the land use dynamics arising in producing landscapes are taken into account. Impact assessments of value chains involving an agricultural phase need to complement farm-level accounting methods with tools able to capture the land use change impacts caused by agriculture beyond the farm-level. Land use modelling and fine-scale spatial assessments can help the assessment of these context-specific land use dynamics. Due to its lower yields, cocoa agroforestry performed worse than those of cocoa full-sun according to most impact indicators (except for biodiversity and human toxicity). However, positive impacts for biodiversity and carbon stocks could be achieved with cocoa agroforestry if sustainable intensification and forest protection policies are implemented in cocoa producing landscapes. The impacts on biodiversity and carbon stocks at the landscape-level can be worse than those at the farm-level or even show

contrary results (e.g. carbon gains at the landscape-level versus carbon losses at the farm-level) due to changes in spatial configuration of the landscape. Our results showed that, due to socioeconomic systems in which cocoa production is embedded, the close cooperation between private and public actors is needed to solve sustainability issues in cocoa value-chains using integrated landscape-based approaches.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Claudia Parra Paitan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Peter H. Verburg:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154032>.

References

- Abdul, I., Jassogne, L., Graefe, S., Asare, R., Van Asten, P., Läderach, P., Vaast, P., 2018. Characterization of cocoa production, income diversification and shade tree management along a climate gradient in Ghana. *PLoS One* 13, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195777>.
- Alkemade, R., Van Oorschot, M., Miles, L., Nellemann, C., Bakkenes, M., Ten Brink, B., 2009. GLOBIO3: a framework to investigate options for reducing global terrestrial biodiversity loss. *Ecosystems* 12, 374–390. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-009-9229-5>.
- Andres, C., Comoé, H., Beerli, A., Schneider, M., Rist, S., Jacobi, J., 2016. Cocoa in Monoculture and Dynamic Agroforestry. Springer, Cham, pp. 121–153 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-26777-7_3.
- Asare, R., Markussen, B., Asare, R.A., Anim-Kwapong, G., Ræbild, A., 2019. On-farm cocoa yields increase with canopy cover of shade trees in two agro-ecological zones in Ghana. *Clim. Dev.* 11, 435–445. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2018.1442805>.
- Barnes, A.D., Allen, K., Kreft, H., Corre, M.D., Jochum, M., Veldkamp, E., Clough, Y., Daniel, R., Darras, K., Denmead, L.H., Haneda, N.F., Hertel, D., Knohl, A., Kotowska, M.M., Kurniawan, S., Meijide, A., Rembold, K., Prabowo, W.E., Schneider, D., Tschardtke, T., Brose, U., 2017. Direct and cascading impacts of tropical land-use change on multi-trophic biodiversity. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 1(1), 1511–1519. <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41559-017-0275-7>.
- Blaser, W.J., Oppong, J., Yeboah, E., Six, J., 2017. Shade trees have limited benefits for soil fertility in cocoa agroforests. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 243, 83–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.04.007>.
- Blaser, W.J., Oppong, J., Hart, S.P., Landolt, J., Yeboah, E., Six, J., 2018. Climate-smart sustainable agriculture in low-to-intermediate shade agroforests. *Nat. Sustain.* 1, 234–239. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0062-8>.
- Blonk Consultants, 2019a. Agri-footprint 5.0 Part 2: description of data [WWW document]. URL: <https://www.agri-footprint.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Agri-Footprint-5.0-Part-2-Description-of-data-17-7-2019-for-web.pdf>.
- Blonk Consultants, 2019b. Agri-footprint 5.0 Part 1: Methodology and Basic Principles.
- Blonk Consultants, 2021. LUC Impact Tool. Gouda, Netherlands.
- Boshoven, J., Fleck, L.C., Miltner, S., Salafsky, N., Adams, J., Dahl-Jørgensen, A., Fonseca, G., Nepsted, D., Rabinovitch, K., Seymour, F., Dahl-Jørgensen, A., Fonseca, G., Nepsted, D., Rabinovitch, K., Seymour, F., 2021. Jurisdictional sourcing: leveraging commodity supply chains to reduce tropical deforestation at scale. A generic theory of change for a conservation strategy, v 1.0. *Conserv. Sci. Pract.* 3, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.383>.

- Boström, M., Jönsson, A.M., Lockie, S., Mol, A.P.J., Oosterveer, P., 2015. Sustainable and responsible supply chain governance: challenges and opportunities. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 1–7 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.11.050>.
- BSI, 2012. PAS 2050-1:2012. Assessment of Life Cycle Greenhouse Gas Emissions From Horticultural Products, British Standards Institution. British Standards Institution.
- Bulle, C., Margni, M., Patouillard, L., Boulay, A.-M., Bourgault, G., De Bruille, V., Cao, V., Hauschild, M., Henderson, A., Humbert, S., Kashif-Haghighi, S., Kounina, A., Laurent, A., Levasseur, A., Liard, G., Rosenbaum, R.K., Roy, P.-O., Shaked, S., Fantke, P., Jolliet, O., 2019. IMPACT World + : a globally regionalized life cycle impact assessment method. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 24, 1653–1674. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-019-01583-0>.
- Bymolt, R., Laven, A., Tyszler, M., 2018. Demystifying the Cocoa Sector in Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire. The Royal Tropical Institute (KIT), Amsterdam.
- Carodenuto, S., 2019. Governance of zero deforestation cocoa in West Africa: new forms of public-private interaction. *Environ. Policy Gov.* 29, 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1841>.
- Chaplin-Kramer, R., Sharp, R.P., Mandl, L., Sim, S., Johnson, J., Butnar, I., Milà i Canals, L., Eichelberger, B.A., Ramler, I., Mueller, C., McLachlan, N., Yousefi, A., King, H., Kareiva, P.M., 2015. Spatial patterns of agricultural expansion determine impacts on biodiversity and carbon storage. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112, 7402–7407. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1406485112>.
- Chaplin-Kramer, R., Sim, S., Hamel, P., Bryant, B., Noe, R., Mueller, C., Rigalsford, G., Kulak, M., Kowal, V., Sharp, R., Clavreul, J., Price, E., Polasky, S., Ruckelshaus, M., Daily, G., 2017. Life cycle assessment needs predictive spatial modelling for biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms15065>.
- Chaudhary, A., Veronesi, F., De Baan, L., Hellweg, S., 2015. Quantifying land use impacts on biodiversity: combining species-area models and vulnerability indicators. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49, 9987–9995. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b02507>.
- Cole, L.E.S., Bhagwat, S.A., Willis, K.J., 2014. Recovery and resilience of tropical forests after disturbance. *Nat. Commun.* 5(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms4906>.
- Corré, W.J., 2002. Agricultural Land Use and Emissions of CH4 and N2O in Europe Wageningen.
- Costa, M.P., Chadwick, D., Saget, S., Rees, R.M., Williams, M., Styles, D., 2020. Representing crop rotations in life cycle assessment: a review of legume LCA studies. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 25(10), 1942–1956. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-020-01812-X>.
- Crawford, R.H., Bontinck, P.A., Stephan, A., Wiedmann, T., Yu, M., 2018. Hybrid life cycle inventory methods – a review. *J. Clean. Prod.* 172, 1273–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.176>.
- Crenna, E., Marques, A., La Notte, A., Sala, S., 2020. Biodiversity assessment of value chains: state of the art and emerging challenges. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54, 9715–9728. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b05153>.
- Crippa, M., Solazzo, E., Guizzardi, D., Monforti-Ferrario, F., Tubiello, F.N., Leip, A., 2021. Food systems are responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nat. Food* 2(2), 198–209. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9>.
- Cucurachi, S., Scherer, L., Guinée, J., Tukker, A., 2019. Life cycle assessment of food systems. *One Earth* 1, 292–297.
- Curran, M.A., 2014. Strengths and Limitations of Life Cycle Assessment. *LCA Compendium - The Complete World of Life Cycle Assessment*. Springer, Dordrecht, pp. 189–206 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8697-3_6.
- Dave, R., Saint-Laurent, C., Murray, L., Antunes Daldegan, G., Brouwer, R., de Mattos Scaramuzza, C.A., Raes, L., Simonit, S., Catapan, M., García Contreras, G., Ndoli, A., Karangwa, C., Perera, N., Hingorani, S., Pearson, T., 2019. Second Bonn Challenge Progress Report. Application of the Barometer in 2018, Second Bonn Challenge Progress Report: Application of the Barometer in 2018 <https://doi.org/10.2305/iucn.ch.2019.06.en>.
- De Baan, L., Mutel, C.L., Curran, M., Hellweg, S., Koellner, T., 2013. Land use in life cycle assessment: global characterization factors based on regional and global potential species extinction. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47, 9281–9290. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es400592q>.
- De Rosa, M., 2018. Land use and land-use changes in life cycle assessment: green modelling or black boxing? *Ecol. Econ.* 144, 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.07.017>.
- Di Lucia, L., Ahlgren, S., Ericsson, K., 2012. The dilemma of indirect land-use changes in EU biofuel policy – an empirical study of policy-making in the context of scientific uncertainty. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 16, 9–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2011.11.004>.
- Dijkman, T.J., Birkved, M., Hauschild, M.Z., 2012. Pest.CI 2.0: a second generation model for estimating emissions of pesticides from arable land in LCA. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 17, 973–986. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-012-0439-2>.
- Dullinger, I., Essl, F., Moser, D., Erb, K., Haberl, H., Dullinger, S., 2021. Biodiversity models need to represent land-use intensity more comprehensively. *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* 30, 924–932. <https://doi.org/10.1111/GEB.13289>.
- Earles, J.M., Halog, A., 2011. Consequential life cycle assessment: a review. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 16, 445–453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-011-0275-9>.
- Erb, K.-H., Luysaert, S., Meyfroidt, P., Pongratz, J., Don, A., Kloster, S., Kuemmerle, T., Fetzel, T., Fuchs, R., Herold, M., Haberl, H., Jones, C.D., Marín-Spiotta, E., McCallum, I., Robertson, E., Seufert, V., Fritz, S., Valade, A., Wiltshire, A., Dolman, A.J., 2017. Land management: data availability and process understanding for global change studies. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 23, 512–533. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13443>.
- FAO, 2014. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015. Country Report Ghana.
- FAOSTAT, 2020. FAOSTAT [WWW document]. URL Food Agric. Organ. United Nations FAOSTAT database (accessed 10.13.20) <http://www.fao.org/faostat/>.
- Finkbeiner, M., 2014. Indirect land use change - help beyond the hype? *Biomass Bioenergy* 62, 218–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.01.024>.
- Finkbeiner, M., Ackermann, R., Bach, V., Berger, M., Brankatschk, G., Chang, Y.-J., Grinberg, M., Lehmann, A., Martínez-Blanco, J., Minkov, N., Neugebauer, S., Scheumann, R., Schneider, L., Wolf, K., 2014. Challenges in life cycle assessment: an overview of current gaps and research needs. *LCA Compendium - The Complete World of Life Cycle Assessment*. Springer, Dordrecht, pp. 207–258 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8697-3_7.
- Foley, J.A., DeFries, R., Asner, G.P., Barford, C., Bonan, G., Carpenter, S.R., Chapin, F.S., Coe, M.T., Daily, G.C., Gibbs, H.K., Helkowski, J.H., Holloway, T., Howard, E.A., Kucharik, C.J., Monfreda, C., Patz, J.A., Prentice, I.C., Ramankutty, N., Snyder, P.K., 2005. Global consequences of land use. *Science* (80-) 309, 570–574. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1111772>.
- Folke, C., Österblom, H., Jouffray, J.B., Lambin, E.F., Adger, W.N., Scheffer, M., Crona, B.I., Nyström, M., Levin, S.A., Carpenter, S.R., Anderies, J.M., Chapin, S., Crépin, A.S., Dauriach, A., Galaz, V., Gordon, L.J., Kautsky, N., Walker, B.H., Watson, J.R., Wilen, J., de Zeeuw, A., 2019. Transnational corporations and the challenge of biosphere stewardship. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 3, 1396–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0978-z>.
- Forestry Commission, 2015. Ghana National REDD+ Strategy.
- Forestry Commission, 2016. Ghana Forest Plantation Strategy: 2016 - 2040.
- Forestry Commission, 2017. Ghana's National Forest Reference Level.
- Fountain, A.C., Huetz-Adams, F., 2020. Cocoa Barometer 2020.
- Frankl, P., Rubik, F., 2000. Life Cycle Assessment in Industry and Business. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin.
- Gardner, T.A., Benzie, M., Börner, J., Dawkins, E., Fick, S., Garrett, R., Godar, J., Grimard, A., Lake, S., Larsen, R.K., Mardas, N., McDermott, C.L., Meyfroidt, P., Osbeck, M., Persson, M., Sembres, T., Suavet, C., Strassburg, B., Trevisan, A., West, C., Wolvenkamp, P., 2018. Transparency and sustainability in global commodity supply chains. *World Dev.* 121, 163–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.05.025>.
- Garrett, R.D., Lambin, E.F., Naylor, R.L., 2013. Land institutions and supply chain configurations as determinants of soybean planted area and yields in Brazil. *Land Use Policy* 31, 385–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.08.002>.
- Ghana Statistical Service, 2019. CountrySTAT Ghana [WWW document]. URL <http://ghana.countrystat.org/> (accessed 10.13.19).
- Godar, J., Suavet, C., Gardner, T.A., Dawkins, E., Meyfroidt, P., 2016. Balancing detail and scale in assessing transparency to improve the governance of agricultural commodity supply chains. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 11, 35015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/3/035015>.
- Goldman, E., Weisse, M.J., Harris, N., Schneider, M., 2020. Estimating the Role of Seven Commodities in Agriculture-Linked Deforestation: Oil Palm, Soy, Cattle, Wood Fiber, Cocoa, Coffee, and Rubber. Technical Note. World Resources Institute, Washington, DC <https://doi.org/10.46830/writn.a.00001>.
- Haas, G., Wetterich, F., Geier, U., 2000. Life cycle assessment framework in agriculture on the farm level. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 5, 345–348. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02978669>.
- Hansen, M.C., Potapov, P.V., Moore, R., Hancher, M., Turubanova, S.A., Tyukavina, A., Thau, D., Stehman, S.V., Goetz, S.J., Loveland, T.R., Kommareddy, A., Egorov, A., Chini, L., Justice, C.O., Townshend, J.R.G., 2013. High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest cover change. *Science* (80-). 342, 850–853. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1244693>.
- Hellweg, S., Canals, L.M.I., 2014. Emerging approaches, challenges and opportunities in life cycle assessment. *Science* (80-) 344, 1109–1113. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1248361>.
- Ibáñez-Forés, V., Pacheco-Blanco, B., Capuz-Rizo, S.F., Bovea, M.D., 2016. Environmental product declarations: exploring their evolution and the factors affecting their demand in Europe. *J. Clean. Prod.* 116, 157–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.12.078>.
- IFPRI, 2017. Extended Results From the International Model for Policy Analysis of Agricultural Commodities and Trade (IMPACT Version 3.2.1) [WWW Document]. Harvard Dataverse, V1., Country Level Data. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/XEZXT4>.
- IIASA, 2020. SSP database (shared socioeconomic pathways)-version 2.0 [WWW document]. URL <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=10> (accessed 9.15.20).
- Ingram, V., van Rijn, F., Waarts, Y., Gilhuis, H., 2018. The impacts of cocoa sustainability initiatives in West Africa. *Sustainability* 10, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10114249>.
- IPCC, 2019a. Climate Change and Land: An IPCC Special Report on Climate Change, Desertification, Land Degradation, Sustainable Land Management, Food Security, and Greenhouse Gas Fluxes in Terrestrial Ecosystems.
- IPCC, 2019b. 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. URL (accessed 10.13.19).
- Isaac, M.E., Timmer, V.R., Quashie-Sam, S.J., 2007. Shade tree effects in an 8-year-old cocoa agroforestry system: biomass and nutrient diagnosis of Theobroma cacao by vector analysis. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosyst.* 78, 155–165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-006-9081-3>.
- ISO 14044, 2006. Environmental Management. Life Cycle Assessment. Requirements and Guidelines. First edit. Geneva.
- Jacobi, J., Andres, C., Schneider, M., Pillco, M., Calizaya, P., Rist, S., 2014. Carbon stocks, tree diversity, and the role of organic certification in different cocoa production systems in Alto Beni, Bolivia. *Agrofor. Syst.* 88, 1117–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-013-9643-8>.
- Jolliet, O., Antón, A., Boulay, A.-M.M., Cherubini, F., Fantke, P., Levasseur, A., McKone, T.E., Michelsen, O., Milà i Canals, L., Motoshita, M., Pfister, S., Veronesi, F., Vigon, B., Frischknecht, R., 2018. Global guidance on environmental life cycle impact assessment indicators: impacts of climate change, fine particulate matter formation, water consumption and land use. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 23, 2189–2207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-018-1443-y>.
- JRC-IES, 2010. International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook - General Guide for Life Cycle Assessment - Detailed Guidance. <https://doi.org/10.2788/38479> Luxembourg.
- Kleppel, G.S., 2020. Do differences in livestock management practices influence environmental impacts? *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.*, 141 <https://doi.org/10.3389/FSUFS.2020.00141>.
- Kløverpris, J.H., Scheel, C.N., Schmidt, J., Grant, B., Smith, W., Bentham, M.J., 2020. Assessing life cycle impacts from changes in agricultural practices of crop production methodological description and case study of microbial phosphate inoculant. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 25, 1991–2007. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-020-01767-z>.
- Knudsen, M.T.M.T., Dorca-Preda, T., Djomo, S.N.S.N., Peña, N., Padel, S., Smith, L.G., Zollitsch, W., Hörtenhuber, S., Hermansen, J.E., 2020. The importance of including soil carbon changes, ecotoxicity and biodiversity impacts in environmental life cycle

- assessment of organic and conventional milk in Western Europe. *J. Clean. Prod.* 215, 433–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.273>.
- Koch, P., Salou, T., 2014. AGRIBALYSE: Methodology, Version 1.1 384.
- Koellner, T., Scholz, R.R.W., 2007. Assessment of land use impacts on the natural environment: part 1: an analytical framework for pure land occupation and land use change. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 12, 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.1065/lca2006.12.292.1>.
- Kongsager, R., Napier, J., Mertz, O., 2013. The carbon sequestration potential of tree crop plantations. *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Chang.* 18, 1197–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-012-9417-z>.
- Lambin, E.F., Turner, B.L., Geist, H.J., Agbola, S.B., Angelsen, A., Folke, C., Bruce, J.W., Coomes, O.T., Dirzo, R., George, P.S., Homewood, K., Imbernon, J., Leemans, R., Li, X., Moran, E.F., Mortimore, M., Ramakrishnan, P.S., Richards, J.F., Steffen, W., Stone, G.D., Svedin, U., Veldkamp, T.A., Vogel, C., Xu, J., 2001. The causes of land-use and land-cover change: moving beyond the myths. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 11, 261–269. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780\(01\)00007-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780(01)00007-3).
- Lambin, E.F., Gibbs, H.K., Heilmayr, R., Carlson, K.M., Fleck, L.C., Garrett, R.D., Le Polain De Waroux, Y., McDermott, C.L., McLaughlin, D., Newton, P., Nolte, C., Pacheco, P., Rausch, L.L., Streck, C., Thurlakson, T., Walker, N.F., 2018. The role of supply-chain initiatives in reducing deforestation. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 8, 109–116. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-017-0061-1>.
- Lapola, D.M., Schaldach, R., Alcamo, J., Bondeau, A., Koch, J., Koelking, C., Priess, J.A., 2010. Indirect land-use changes can overcome carbon savings from biofuels in Brazil. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 107, 3388–3393. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.0907318107>.
- Liu, J., Yang, W., Li, S., Hull, V., Batistella, M., DeFries, R., Dietz, T., Fu, F., Hertel, T.W., Izaurralde, R.C., Lambin, E.F., Li, S., Martinelli, L.A., McConnell, W.J., Moran, E.F., Naylor, R., Ouyang, Z., Polenske, K.R., Reenberg, A., de Miranda Rocha, G., Simmons, C.S., Verburg, P.H., Vitousek, P.M., Zhang, F., Zhu, C., 2013. Framing sustainability in a telecoupled world. *Ecol. Soc.* 18, 26. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05873-180226>.
- Lozano, R., 2020. Analysing the use of tools, initiatives, and approaches to promote sustainability in corporations. *Corp. Soc. Responsib. Environ. Manag.* 27, 982–998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1860>.
- Magliocca, N.R., Khuc, Q.Van, de Bremond, A., Ellicott, E.A., 2020. Direct and indirect land-use change caused by large-scale land acquisitions in Cambodia. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 15, 024010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/AB6397>.
- Martin, P.A., Newton, A.C., Bullock, J.M., 2013. Carbon pools recover more quickly than plant biodiversity in tropical secondary forests. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 280. <https://doi.org/10.1098/RSPB.2013.2236>.
- McManus, M.C., Taylor, C.M., 2015. The changing nature of life cycle assessment. *Biomass Bioenergy* 82, 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2015.04.024>.
- Meyfroidt, P., Lambin, E.F., Erb, K.H., Hertel, T.W., 2013. Globalization of land use: distant drivers of land change and geographic displacement of land use. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 5, 438–444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.04.003>.
- Meyfroidt, P., Roy Chowdhury, R., de Bremond, A., Ellis, E.C.C., Erb, K.-H.H., Filatova, T., Garrett, R.D.D., Grove, J.M.M., Heinemann, A., Kuemmerle, T., Kull, C.A.A., Lambin, E.F.F., Landon, Y., Le Polain de Waroux, Y., Messerli, P., Müller, D., Nielsen, J.O., Peterson, G.D.D., Rodríguez García, V., Schlüter, M., Turner, B.L.L., Verburg, P.H.H., 2018. Middle-range theories of land system change. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 53, 52–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.08.006>.
- Milà i Canals, L., Bauer, C., Depestele, J., Dubreuil, A., Knuchel, R.F., Gaillard, G., Michelsen, O., Müller-Wenk, R., Rydgren, B., 2007. Key elements in a framework for land use impact assessment within LCA. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 12, 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1065/lca2006.05.250>.
- Millard, J., Outhwaite, C.L., Kinnersley, R., Freeman, R., Gregory, R.D., Adedjoja, O., Gavini, S., Kioko, E., Kuhlmann, M., Ollerton, J., Ren, Z.-X., Newbold, T., 2021. Global effects of land-use intensity on local pollinator biodiversity. *Nat. Commun.* 12(12), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23228-3>.
- Ministry of Food and Agriculture of Ghana, 2016. *Agriculture in Ghana. Facts and figures 2015*.
- Mortimer, R., Saj, S., David, C., Mortimer, R., Saj, S., David, C., 2018. Supporting and regulating ecosystem services in cacao agroforestry systems. *Agrofor. Syst.* 92, 1639–1657. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0113-6>.
- Natural Capital Project, 2020. *INVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs)* [WWW document]. URL <https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest> (accessed 10.12.20).
- Nemecek, T., Kagi, T., 2007. *Life Cycle Inventories of Agricultural Production Systems*, Ecoinvent Report No. 15. URL (accessed 10.12.20).
- Nemecek, T., Schnetzer, J., 2011. *Methods of assessment of direct field emissions for LCIs of agricultural production systems. Data quality guideline for ecoinvent database version 3.0.* URL Agroscope Reckenholz-Tänikon Res. Stn. ART 0, p. 34 (accessed 10.13.20).
- Notarnicola, B., Sala, S., Anton, A., McLaren, S.J., Saouter, E., Sonesson, U., 2017. The role of life cycle assessment in supporting sustainable agri-food systems: a review of the challenges. *J. Clean. Prod.* 140, 399–409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.071>.
- Ntiamoah, A., 2009. *Life Cycle Assessment Applied to Chocolate Production in Ghana*. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST).
- Ntiamoah, A., Afrane, G., 2008. Environmental impacts of cocoa production and processing in Ghana: life cycle assessment approach. *J. Clean. Prod.* 16, 1735–1740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2007.11.004>.
- Onat, N., Kucukvar, M., Halog, A., Cloutier, S., 2017. Systems thinking for life cycle sustainability assessment: a review of recent developments, applications, and future perspectives. *Sustainability* 9, 706. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9050706>.
- O'Neill, B.C., Kriegler, E., Ebi, K.L., Kemp-Benedict, E., Riahi, K., Rothman, D.S., van Ruijven, B.J., van Vuuren, D.P., Birkmann, J., Kok, K., Levy, M., Solecki, W., 2017. The roads ahead: narratives for shared socioeconomic pathways describing world futures in the 21st century. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 42, 169–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.01.004>.
- Othoniel, B., Rugani, B., Heijungs, R., Beyer, M., Machwitz, M., Post, P., 2019. An improved life cycle impact assessment principle for assessing the impact of land use on ecosystem services. *Sci. Total Environ.* 693, 133374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.180>.
- Palmer, J., Owens, S., 2015. Indirect land-use change and biofuels: the contribution of assemblage theory to place-specific environmental governance. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 53, 18–26.
- Parra Paitan, C., Verburg, P.H., 2019. Methods to assess the impacts and indirect land use change caused by telecoupled agricultural supply chains: a review. *Sustainability* 11, 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11041162>.
- Pendrill, F., Persson, U.M., Godar, J., Kastner, T., 2019. Deforestation displaced: trade in forest-risk commodities and the prospects for a global forest transition. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 14, 055003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab0d41>.
- Perminova, T., Sirina, N., Laratte, B., Baranovskaya, N., Rikhvanov, L., 2016. Methods for land use impact assessment: a review. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 60, 64–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2016.02.002>.
- Phalan, B., Onial, M., Balmford, A., Green, R.E., 2011. Reconciling food production and biodiversity conservation: land sharing and land sparing compared. *Science* (80-) 333, 1289–1291. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1208742>.
- Prapasongsa, T., Gheewala, S.H., 2016. Risks of indirect land use impacts and greenhouse gas consequences: an assessment of Thailand's bioethanol policy. *J. Clean. Prod.* 134, 563–573.
- Prasuhn, V., 2006. *Erfassung der PO4-Austräge für die Ökobilanzierung - SALCA-Phosphor*. Agroscope Reckenholz, p. 20.
- Prox, M., Curran, M.A., 2017. *Consequential Life Cycle Assessment*, pp. 145–160. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-024-0855-3_4.
- Raschio, G., Smetana, S., Contreras, C., Heinz, V., Mathys, A., 2018. Spatio-temporal differentiation of life cycle assessment results for average perennial crop farm: a case study of peruvian cocoa progression and deforestation issues. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 22, 1378–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12692>.
- Reap, J., Roman, F., Duncan, S., Bras, B., 2008a. A survey of unresolved problems in life cycle assessment. Part 2: impact assessment and interpretation. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 13, 374–388. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-008-0009-9>.
- Reap, J., Roman, F., Duncan, S., Bras, B., 2008b. A survey of unresolved problems in life cycle assessment. Part 1: goal and scope and inventory analysis. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 13, 290–300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-008-0008-x>.
- Republic of Ghana, 2017. *Announcement of Ghana's National Voluntary Contribution to Achieving the Targets of the Global Forest Goals for the United Nations Strategic Plans on Forests 2017–2020*.
- Riahi, K., van Vuuren, D.P., Kriegler, E., Edmonds, J., O'Neill, B.C., Fujimori, S., Bauer, N., Calvin, K., Dellink, R., Fricko, O., Lutz, W., Popp, A., Cuaresma, J.C., KC, S., Leimbach, M., Jiang, L., Kram, T., Rao, S., Emmerling, J., Ebi, K., Hasegawa, T., Havlik, P., Humpenöder, F., Da Silva, L.A., Smith, S., Stehfest, E., Bosetti, V., Eom, J., Gernaat, D., Masui, T., Rogelj, J., Strefler, J., Drouet, L., Krey, V., Luderer, G., Harmsen, M., Takahashi, K., Baumstark, L., Doelman, J.C., Kainuma, M., Klimont, Z., Marangoni, G., Lotze-Campen, H., Obersteiner, M., Tabeau, A., Tavoni, M., 2017. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: an overview. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 42, 153–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.05.009>.
- Richards, P., 2021. A key ingredient in deforestation slowdowns? A strong Brazilian economy. *Front. For. Glob. Chang.* 4, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2021.613313>.
- Richards, P.D., Walker, R.T., Arima, E.Y., 2014. Spatially complex land change: the indirect effect of Brazil's agricultural sector on land use in Amazonia. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 29, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2014.06.011>.
- Roca, L.C., Searcy, C., 2012. An analysis of indicators disclosed in corporate sustainability reports. *J. Clean. Prod.* 20, 103–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.08.002>.
- Roy, P., Nei, D., Orikasa, T., Xu, Q., Okadome, H., Nakamura, N., Shiina, T., 2009. A review of life cycle assessment (LCA) on some food products. *J. Food Eng.* 90, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2008.06.016>.
- Ruf, F.O., 2011. The myth of complex cocoa agroforests: the case of Ghana. *Hum. Ecol.* 39, 373–388. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-011-9392-0>.
- Sala, S., Farioli, F., Zamagni, A., 2013. Life cycle sustainability assessment in the context of sustainability science progress (part 2). *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 18, 1686–1697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-012-0509-5>.
- Salifu, F.K., 1997. *Physico-chemical Properties of Soils Associated With Logged Forest and Areas Converted to Teak (Tectona grandis Linn. F.) in Ghana*. Lakehead Univ. Lakehead University.
- Schmidt, J.H., Weidema, B.P., Brandão, M., 2015. A framework for modelling indirect land use changes in life cycle assessment. *J. Clean. Prod.* 99, 230–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.03.013>.
- Schulze, K., Malek, Ž., Verburg, P.H., 2019. Towards better mapping of forest management patterns: a global allocation approach. *For. Ecol. Manag.* 432, 776–785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FORECO.2018.10.001>.
- Searchinger, T., Heimlich, R., Houghton, R.A., Dong, F., Elobeid, A., Fabiosa, J., Tokgoz, S., Hayes, D., Yu, T., 2008. Use of U.S. croplands for biofuels increases greenhouse gases through emissions from land-use change. *Science* (80-) 423, 1238–1240.
- Seufert, V., Ramankutty, N., 2017. Many shades of grey – the context - dependent performance of organic agriculture. *Sci. Adv.* 1–50.
- Sharp, R., Tallis, H.T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A.D., Wood, S.A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Nelson, E., D, E., Wolny, S., Olwero, N., Vigerstol, K., Pennington, D., Mendoza, G., Aukema, J., Foster, J., Forrest, J., Cameron, D., Arkema, K., Lonsdorf, E., Kennedy, C., Verutes, G., Kim, C.K., Guannel, G., Papefufus, M., Toft, J., Marsik, M., Bernhardt, J., Griffin, R., Glowinski, K., Chaumont, N., Perelman, A., Lacayo, M., Mandle, L., Hamel, P., Vogl, A.L., Rogers, L., Bierbower, W., Denu, D., Douglass, J., 2018. *INVEST User Guide, National Capital Project*.
- Somé, A., Dandres, T., Gaudreault, C., Majeau-Bettez, G., Wood, R., Samson, R., 2018. Coupling input-output tables with macro-life cycle assessment to assess worldwide impacts

- of biofuels transport policies. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 22, 643–655. <https://doi.org/10.1111/JIEC.12640>.
- Stewart, R., Fantke, P., Bjørn, A., Owsianiak, M., Molin, C., Hauschild, M.Z., Laurent, A., 2018. Life cycle assessment in corporate sustainability reporting: global, regional, sectoral, and company-level trends. *Bus. Strateg. Environ.* 27, 1751–1764. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2241>.
- Sulser, T.B., Mason-D’Croz, D., Islam, S., Robinson, S., Wiebe, K.D., Rosegrant, M.W., 2015. *Africa in the Global Agricultural Economy in 2030 and 2050 - IFPRI Publications - IFPRI Knowledge Collections*. Washington, D.C.
- Teillard, F., Maia de Souza, D., Thoma, G., Gerber, P.J., Finn, J.A., 2016. What does life-cycle assessment of agricultural products need for more meaningful inclusion of biodiversity? *J. Appl. Ecol.* 53, 1422–1429. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12683>.
- Turner, B.L., Meyfroidt, P., Kuemmerle, T., Müller, D., Roy Chowdhury, R., 2020. Framing the search for a theory of land use. *J. Land Use Sci.* 15, 489–508. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1747423X.2020.1811792>.
- Tutu Benefoh, D., Villamor, G.B., van Noordwijk, M., Borgemeister, C., Asante, W.A., Asubonteng, K.O., 2018. Assessing land-use typologies and change intensities in a structurally complex Ghanaian cocoa landscape. *Appl. Geogr.* 99, 109–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2018.07.027>.
- UNEP-SETAC, 2016. *Global Guidance for Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators*. Volume 1. United Nations Environment Programme.
- UNEP-SETAC, 2019. *Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators*. Volume 2. United Nations Environment Programme.
- UN-OCHA, 2020. *Ghana-roads* [WWW document]. Humanit. Data exch. <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/ghana-roads>.
- Van Asselen, S., Verburg, P.H., 2013. Land cover change or land-use intensification: simulating land system change with a global-scale land change model. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 19, 3648–3667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12331>.
- van der Werf, H.M.G., Knudsen, M.T., Cederberg, C., 2020. Towards better representation of organic agriculture in life cycle assessment. *Nat. Sustain.* 3(3), 419–425. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-0489-6> 2020.
- Veldkamp, E., Purbopuspito, J., Corre, M.D., Brumme, R., Murdiyarso, D., 2008. Land use change effects on trace gas fluxes in the forest margins of Central Sulawesi, Indonesia. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosci.* 113, 2003. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JG000522>.
- Verchot, L.V., Dannenmann, M., Kengdo, S.K., Njine-Bememba, C.B., Rufino, M.C., Sonwa, D.J., Tejedor, J., 2020. Land-use Change and Biogeochemical Controls of Soil CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ Fluxes in Cameroonian Forest Landscapes, pp. 45–67 <https://doi.org/10.1080/1943815X.2020.1779092> doi:10.1080/1943815X.2020.1779092.
- Veronesi, F., Hellweg, S., Antón, A., Azevedo, L.B., Chaudhary, A., Cosme, N., Cucurachi, S., de Baan, L., Dong, Y., Fantke, P., Golsteijn, L., Hauschild, M., Heijungs, R., Jolliet, O., Juraske, R., Larsen, H., Laurent, A., Mutel, C.L., Margni, M., Núñez, M., Owsianiak, M., Pfister, S., Ponsioen, T., Preiss, P., Rosenbaum, R.K., Roy, P.O., Sala, S., Steinmann, Z., van Zelm, R., Van Dingenen, R., Vieira, M., Huijbregts, M.A.J., 2020. LC-IMPACT: a regionalized life cycle damage assessment method. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 24, 1201–1219. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13018>.
- von Essen, M., Lambin, E.F., von Essen, M., Lambin, E.F., 2021. Jurisdictional approaches to sustainable resource use. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 19, 159–167. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2299>.
- Weidema, B.P., 2003. *Market Information in Life Cycle Assessment*. Danish Environmental Protection Agency.
- Weidema, B.P., Bauder, C., Hischer, R., Mutel, C., Nemecek, T., Reinhard, J., V.C., O., Wernet, G., 2013. *Overview and methodology. Data Quality Guideline for the Ecoinvent Database Version 3*. St. Gallen.
- Wessel, M., Quist-Wessel, P.M.F., 2015. Cocoa production in West Africa, a review and analysis of recent developments. *NJAS - Wageningen J. Life Sci.* 74–75, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.njas.2015.09.001>.
- Winter, L., Lehmann, A., Finogenova, N., Finkbeiner, M., 2017. Including biodiversity in life cycle assessment – state of the art, gaps and research needs. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 67, 88–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2017.08.006>.
- Wolff, S., Meijer, J., Schulp, C.J.E., Verburg, P.H., 2020. Contextualizing local landscape initiatives in global change: a scenario study for the high forest zone, Ghana. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 20, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-020-01701-x>.
- Wu, S.R., Liu, X., Wang, L., Chen, J., Zhou, P., 2021. Integrating Life Cycle Assessment Into Landscape Studies: A Postcard From Hulunbuir. <https://doi.org/10.21203/RS.3.RS-287195/V1>.